

Title: Supercharging blockchain adoption

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INTRODUCTION:

A realistic assessment of the challenges facing blockchain and decentralized startups competing with their centralized competitors, as well as potential solutions to the problem.

AIM:

To evaluate the competitive landscape the thousands of distributed applications currently undergoing ICOs will compete in.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Market data, primary and secondary analysis as well as first-hand experience garnered from 10 years in the field

RESULTS:

N/A

CONCLUSIONS:

If blockchain startups are really going to disrupt their respective sectors, they are going to require a new approach to user growth and product development.

KEYWORDS:

Blockchain adoption, marketing, ICO, distributed applications

BIOGRAPHY:

Jan Sammut is the founder and CEO of RefToken, the worlds first decentralised affiliate platform, as well as ICOMalta, a full stack ICO hosting provider. A marketer by profession, he has previously held executive positions at industry heavyweights such as IGT plc, Stars Group and Highlight Media Group.